

Utilization of Turpentine : Dehydrogenation of Δ^3 -Carene over Platinum-Alumina in Presence of Nitrogen, Hydrogen, Pyridine and *n*-Butylamine

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3-Carene has been dehydrogenated over platinum-alumina catalyst in vapour phase in a flow reactor at various contact times and partial pressures. The influence of contact time shows that 3-carene initially isomerises to *p*- and *m*-menthadienes which subsequently undergo dehydrogenation and disproportionation. Nitrogen acts as a diluent while hydrogen acts as a diluent and as a promotor. Pyridine and *n*-butylamine suppress the reaction, the suppression is more drastic in the presence of *n*-butylamine.

The reaction of 3-carene follows a first order kinetics. The various types of transformations of 3-carene are explained by a tentative mechanism involving carbonium ion intermediate using Lewis and Brønsted acid sites wherever possible.

TURPENTINE, especially of the Indian origin, is an important raw material for the preparation of chemical intermediates but has not been exploited to the full extent. A major difficulty in its utilisation is the presence of 3-carene, occurring to the extent of 60%, which gets easily oxidised in air with resin formation¹. On account of this the oil cannot be stored for long as an industrial raw material. It is used presently as thinner for paints and varnishes. Attempts are being made to convert this unstable material into a mixture of *p*- and *m*-cymenes over chromia and chromia-alumina catalysts²⁻⁵.

Though chromia and chromia-alumina have been widely used as effective aromatisation catalysts, their maximum efficiency occurs in the temperature regions around 500°. In this temperature region, however, the catalysts are prone to undergo sintering and hence a loss of activity. On the other hand platinum, when dispersed over a support like a alumina, brings about aromatisation at a comparatively low temperature region of 250-350°.

In this investigation the dehydrogenation of 3-carene to *p*- and *m*-cymenes has been studied over platinum-alumina (0.6% Pt) dual function catalyst at different contact times, and partial pressures of nitrogen, hydrogen, pyridine and *n*-butylamine. The kinetics and a tentative mechanism have also been proposed. The information regarding the performance of the catalysts described in this article is very useful, as platinum-alumina is being increasingly employed in reforming processes.

Experimental

Alumina was prepared by hydrolysing aluminium *iso*-propoxide with water⁶. Platinum-alumina was obtained by adding calculated volume of chloropla-

tinic acid in water to give 0.6% platinum⁷ (confirmed by spectrophotometric analysis⁸). 3-Carene was isolated from top quality Indian turpentine by fractionation at reduced pressures^{4,5}. Details of the experimental procedure and analysis of the products are given in previous publications^{4,5,7}.

The surface area of alumina (BET) was determined by adsorption of nitrogen at liquid nitrogen temperature⁹, and the value is found to be 121.1 m²/g. The acid strength distribution of alumina was determined by *n*-butylamine titration method developed by Johnson¹⁰, Benesi¹¹ and others¹² using Hammett indicators and the titre values are: butter yellow ($pK_a = +3.3$) 0.29 meq/g, dicinnamalacetone ($pK_a = -3.0$) 0.27 meq/g, chalcone ($pK_a = -5.7$) 0.056 meq/g and anthraquinone ($pK_a = -8.3$) 0.034 meq/g of *n*-butylamine. The Brønsted acidity of alumina was found to be only 0.02 meq/g of iodine by potassium iodide-potassium iodate method¹³. Compared to the total acidity of 0.65 the Brønsted acidity is negligible.

Results and Discussion

Contact time :

The influence of contact time, W/F, (W is the weight of the catalyst and F is the amount of 3-carene fed into the reactor per hour) has been studied at 300° and the results are plotted in Fig. 1. The rates of overall conversion of 3-carene and that of the formation of cymenes are proportional upto 0.8 hr. Between 0.8 to 1.6 hr the change is only negligible. Though the total cymene content increases with contact time, the ratio of *p*-cymene to *m*-cymene (*p*/*m*) remains around 2.0 irrespective of the variation of parameters. Separate studies showed that cymenes undergo neither side chain

Fig. 1. Effect of contact time on product distribution.

dehydrogenation nor ring hydrogenation under the experimental conditions. This shows that cymenes are the final products in the transformation of 3-carene.

The concentration of menthadienes increases initially, registers a maximum below 0.1 hr and then decreases rapidly (Fig. 1). Among the menthadienes, dipentene, sylvestrene, terpinolene, α - and γ -terpinenes have been identified by chemical and gas chromatographic analysis. Since the individual concentrations are too small, their total concentration as menthadienes is given. The corresponding *m*-menthadienes could not be identified owing to the difficulty of further resolution in the chromatograph used.

Menthadienes, in addition to their direct dehydrogenation, undergo disproportionation to menthanes, menthenes and cymenes. Menthanes and menthenes, after exhibiting an initial increase, remain constant (Fig. 1).

The menthanes and menthenes cannot be formed by hydrogenation of menthadienes due to the reasons that (i) the temperature is too high for hydrogenation to occur [this has been confirmed by passing *p*-cymene and hydrogen (200 ml H₂/min) when the amount of menthanes formed was found negligible], and (ii) the volume of hydrogen evolved during the reaction is too small to bring about hydrogenation. Further, the occurrence of disproportionation over this catalyst has been verified by using cyclohexene. Under the experimental conditions 75% of cyclohexene disproportionates giving 50% benzene and 25% cyclohexane. Hence it is concluded that menthanes and menthenes are formed by disproportionation of menthadienes.

Partial pressures :

In order to estimate the extent to which hydrogen, pyridine and *n*-butylamine inhibit or enhance the overall conversion as well as the distribution of

Fig. 2. Effect of partial pressure of nitrogen, hydrogen, pyridine and *n*-butylamine on the overall conversion of 3-carene.

products (due to preferential adsorption) they are compared with the rates obtained in the presence of inert diluent nitrogen (Figs. 2 to 5).

The rates of conversion of 3-carene increase (Fig. 2) with increasing partial pressure of 3-carene in presence of nitrogen and hydrogen upto 0.8 atm. Beyond this value the conversion attains a constant value. It is clear from this that complete coverage of the catalyst surface is achieved at this value and hence further increase of partial pressure has no effect. Nitrogen and hydrogen produce similar trend. This is because hydrogen does not get adsorbed strongly over alumina and only behaves as a diluent like nitrogen with regard to overall conversion.

However, the amount of cymenes formed is more in the presence of hydrogen than in the presence of nitrogen (Fig. 3). The higher amount of cymene

Fig. 3. Effect of partial pressure of nitrogen, hydrogen, pyridine and *n*-butylamine on the formation of cymenes.

formation in the presence of H_2 is due to its promoting action even though it also acts as a diluent. Its promoting action lies in its ability to hydrogenate the unsaturated precursors of coke such as alkylcyclopentadienes that might be formed by the isomerisation of menthadienes over strongly acid sites as reported by Pines *et al*¹⁴. The strong tendency of C_5 ring compounds to polymerise over acid catalysts is well known¹⁵. In presence of hydrogen the catalyst surface is kept clean and

Fig. 4. Effect of partial pressure of nitrogen, hydrogen, pyridine and *n*-butylamine on the formation of menthenes and menthanes.

therefore its dehydrogenation activity is higher. Similar trend is observed in the formation of menthanes and menthenes (Fig. 4). From these observations it is apparent that dehydrogenation and disproportionation of menthadienes occur side by side over platinum metal sites.

Both pyridine and *n*-butylamine suppress the overall conversion of 3-carene, the suppression is more drastic in the presence of *n*-butylamine (Fig. 2). Further, these bases are equally effective in bringing about a decrease in the formation of cymenes (Fig. 3), menthanes and menthenes (Fig. 4). The decrease in the overall activity of the catalyst by pyridine and *n*-butylamine shows that these bases affect both acidic and metal sites. As the function of metal component diminishes by the presence of pyridine and *n*-butylamine, the concentration of menthadienes in the products registers an increase (Fig. 5). This shows that pyridine and *n*-butylamine neutralise strong acid sites, leaving weak sites unaffected as pointed out by Parry¹⁶. The weak sites decyclise the cyclopropane ring of 3-carene to menthadienes. This is not surprising because the cyclopropane ring is shown to be as reactive as an ethylenic double bond by thermochemical data^{17,18}.

The higher decrease in the overall conversion of 3-carene and consequent low concentration of

Fig. 5. Effect of partial pressure of nitrogen, hydrogen, pyridine and *n*-butylamine on the formation of menthadienes.

menthadienes in the product (Fig. 5) by *n*-butylamine as compared to pyridine may be due to its strong basic nature (pK_b for *n*-butylamine and pyridine are 3.39 and 8.96, respectively). The increasing concentration of menthadienes by increasing partial pressure of nitrogen is due to its diluting effect while the diluting effect of hydrogen is adequately compensated by its promoting action. Since the metal sites are readily available in presence of hydrogen as described earlier, the menthadienes undergo further reaction as soon as they are formed.

Kinetics : A plot of $-\ln(1-x)$ against contact time (W/F) gives a straight line passing through the origin showing that the reaction follows first order kinetics. The rate constant calculated from the slope of the straight line plot is given in Table 1

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Temp. K	ΔH^* kJ/mol	ΔS^* J/mol/K	ΔG^* kJ/mol	log PZ	$k \times 10^4$ sec ⁻¹
478	5848.6	-133.75	69110.4	-2.095	6.671
528	5492.9	-134.72	75891.4	-2.167	7.172
578	5017.2	-135.32	82555.5	-2.200	8.096
578	from the slope of the first order plot				7.540
628	4601.5	-135.00	88706.0	-2.125	11.910

along with the values calculated using the first order rate equation at different temperatures. The activation energy was calculated from the Arrhenius plot and the value is 9781.1 kJ/mole. The thermodynamic parameters for the activated complex of the system, through which it passes for the reaction to occur, were obtained using the following equations and the values are also presented in Table 1.

$$\text{Rate constant} = A \exp(-E_a/RT) \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\text{Rate constant} = \frac{kT}{h} \exp(-n) \exp(\Delta S^*/RT) \exp(-E_a/RT) \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = E_a - RT \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\Delta G^\ddagger = \Delta H^\ddagger - T\Delta S^\ddagger \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = R (\ln A - 1 - kT/h) \quad \dots (5)$$

where k is Boltzman's constant, h is Planck's constant, T is absolute temperature, and ΔG^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are the free energy, enthalpy and entropy of activation, respectively.

During the reaction, the molecules got adsorbed on the catalyst surface and were bound tightly to the active sites, as a result of which the activated complex was formed. The loss of mobility or freedom for the activated complex was obvious from the negative value of ΔS^\ddagger .

Mechanism :

Determination of acidity of alumina reveals that the proportion of Brönsted acid sites is negligible compared to total acidity (vide Section 2). The total acidity is assumed to be made up of Brönsted and Lewis acid sites. Even though Lewis acidity seems to constitute a major fraction of the total acidity, its role in bringing about the transformation, especially of the terpene hydrocarbons, has been neglected. In this investigation the various transformations of 3-carene are explained by tentative mechanisms using Brönsted and Lewis acid sites wherever possible.

The formation of α -terpinene which is identified to be the immediate precursor of *p*-cymene is explained over Brönsted acid sites in Scheme A. Proton from the catalyst surface attacks the cyclopropane ring of 3-carene (1) resulting in the formation of carbonium ion (2) and/or (3). Carbonium ion (2) on elimination of a proton from the appropriate carbon atom gives dipentene (4) and terpinolene (5). Carbonium ion (3) similarly eliminates a proton resulting in the formation of sylvestrene (6). α -Terpinene (8) and γ -terpinene (9) are formed from terpinolene (5) by double bond isomerisation through a carbonium ion intermediate (7).

Scheme A

Alternatively, the formation of terpinenes may be explained using Lewis acid sites as detailed in Scheme B. Initially the cyclopropane ring in

3-carene (1) cleaves with the formation of carbonium ion (10), which rearranges to carbonium ion (11) by 1,2-hydride shift. This desorbs from the catalyst surface as γ -terpinene (9). γ -Terpinene may adsorb again in such a way to give carbonium ion (12). By 1,3-hydride shift, it changes to carbonium ion (13) and finally desorbs as α -terpinene (8).

Scheme B

The direct dehydrogenation of α -terpinene to *p*-cymene (14) over platinum metal sites involves the formation of α - (I) and $\alpha\beta$ (II) or π -adsorbed complex (III) followed by stepwise removal of hydrogen atom and the extension of π -system, as suggested by Germain¹⁹, is explained in Scheme C.

Scheme C

Conclusion :

3-Carene is a very cheap and abundantly available raw material that could be used for the manufacture of *p*- and *m*-cymenes. The *p*- and *m*-cymene mixture can be oxidised to tere- and iso-phthalic acid, respectively. Since iso-phthalic acid is soluble in hot water, the acid mixture can be separated by hot water treatment. tere-Phthalic acid is an important raw material for the manufacture of synthetic polyester fibre while iso-phthalic acid is used as an additive in plastics as a heat resistant component. It is to be noted that no substitute for iso-phthalic acid with this unique property has so far been developed. Among the bifunctional catalysts used for this reaction platinum-alumina, especially in the presence of added hydrogen, functions effectively around 300°.

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